

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This is kind of an anniversary issue: the first issue of J.UCS (Vol.0, No.0) was published more or less exactly two years ago! Over those two years almost 2000 pages of high quality scientific papers have appeared in J.UCS: J.UCS has become one of the few electronic journals in computer science with a serious amount of information published in it.

It is time to thank all persons who contributed to J.UCS, all editors and reviewers. I think the fact that J.UCS is going strong and has received a fair amount of praise should encourage all of us to continue our work with enthusiasm. Thus, please keep submitting high quality papers, and ... dear editors!... please continue to help with the often tedious reviewing process.

Hope you will enjoy reading this last-but-one issue of 1996!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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